

TIL ORQALI DUNYOQARASHNING SHAKLLANISHI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada tilning inson tafakkuri va borliqni anglash jarayonidagi mavqei lingvokulturologik nuqtai nazardan tahlil etiladi. Til faqat muloqot vositasi emas, balki kishining dunyoni qanday ko‘rishi, qadrlashi va tasniflashini belgilovchi muhim kognitiv mexanizm sifatida talqin qilinadi. Tadqiqotda “dunyo manzarasining” mohiyati ochib berilib, uning til birliklari leksika, frazeologiya va metaforalar yordamida tarkib topishi ko‘rsatib o‘tiladi. Shuningdek, turli tillarda bir xil hodisaning o‘ziga xos ifodalanishi milliy-madaniy o‘y-fikr bilan uzviy aloqadorligi asoslanadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: dunyo manzarasi, lingvokulturologiya, konsept, til va fikrlash, semantik maydon, madaniy kod, lingvistik tasvir, kognitiv yondashuv, frazeologik birliklar.

Abstract. This article analyzes the role of language in human thinking and understanding of existence from a linguoculturological point of view. Language is interpreted not only as a means of communication, but also as an important cognitive mechanism that determines how a person sees, appreciates and classifies the world. The study reveals the essence of the “worldview” and shows that its linguistic units are formed using lexicon, phraseology and metaphors. It also establishes that the specific expression of the same phenomenon in different languages is inextricably linked with national-cultural thought.

Key words: worldview, linguoculturology, concept, language and thinking, semantic field, cultural code, linguistic image, cognitive approach, phraseological units.

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируется роль языка в человеческом мышлении и понимании существования с лингвокультурологической точки зрения. Язык рассматривается не только как средство коммуникации, но и как важный познавательный механизм, определяющий, как человек видит, воспринимает и классифицирует мир. Исследование раскрывает сущность «мировоззрения» и показывает, что его языковые единицы формируются с использованием лексики, фразеологии и метафор. Также устанавливается, что специфическое выражение одного и того же явления на разных языках неразрывно связано с национально-культурным мышлением.

Ключевые слова: мировоззрение, лингвокультурология, концепция, язык и мышление, семантическое поле, культурный код, лингвистический образ, когнитивный подход, фразеологические единицы.

In modern linguistics, not only the role of language as a communicative tool, but also its active participation in human thinking and perception of existence is becoming increasingly important. In particular, research in the areas of linguoculturology and cognitive linguistics requires studying language in its inextricable connection with the picture of the world that is formed in the human mind. From this point of view, language appears as an important system that reflects how a person perceives the external world, how he classifies and evaluates it.

The concept of “worldview” means a system of generalized ideas about existence that exists in the human mind. This system is expressed through language and is formed in close connection with the historical experience, cultural values, and national thinking of each people. [1]

As a result, different expressions of the same reality are observed in different languages, which once again confirms the inextricable link between language and culture.

This article analyzes the issue of the formation of the worldview through language based on a linguoculturological approach. In particular, the conceptualization of existence through language units - lexical layer, phraseological units and metaphorical expressions - is considered. [2]

It is also substantiated that language not only reflects reality, but also shapes it to a certain extent, using concepts such as concept, semantic field and cultural code.

The relevance of the study is that, in the context of globalization, when communication between different cultures is expanding, a deep understanding of the worldview formed through language serves to increase the effectiveness of intercultural communication. [3]

At the same time, studying this issue is also important in identifying semantic and cultural inconsistencies that arise in the translation process and eliminating them.

Thus, studying the formation of the worldview through language is relevant not only theoretically, but also practically, as it allows for a deeper understanding of the complex relationships between language, thought and culture.

When analyzing the issue of the formation of the worldview through language, it is necessary, first of all, to pay attention to the nominative (naming), cognitive (perception) and interpretative (interpretation) functions of language. [4]

Language does not directly reflect the existence of a person, but expresses it in a certain processed, that is, conceptualized form. Therefore, the worldview is considered as a complex and multi-layered system formed through language.

1. Formation of the worldview through lexical units.

Each language divides and names existence into segments in its own way. For example, in the Uzbek language, units expressing kinship relations are very detailed: *brother, sister, niece, nephew, uncle*. In English, these concepts are more generalized: *brother, sister, uncle*. This indicates that kinship relations occupy an important place in Uzbek society in social and cultural terms. Thus, the lexical composition of the language serves to accurately express concepts that are important for society. [5]

Another example is the names of colors. In Uzbek, the word *ko'k* can sometimes denote both *blue* and *green* colors, while in English these colors are strictly distinguished (*blue* and *green*). This indicates the uniqueness of the language in the process of perceiving and classifying colors.

2. National worldview in phraseological units.

Phraseologisms are one of the most vivid manifestations of the worldview formed through language, because they embody the historical experience and cultural views of the people. For example, the expression *ko'ngli tog'dek* in the Uzbek language means that a person is broad-minded and tolerant. In English, the expression *big-hearted*, which is close to this meaning, is used. Although both languages express the same content, the images are different: in one *mountain*, in the other *big heart*. [6]

Next, Uzbek expression *yuragi orqaga tortdi* means fear or hesitation, while in English this state is expressed by *to lose heart* or *to get cold feet*. These examples show that the same psychological states are conceptualized through different images in different languages.

3. Metaphor and conceptual system.

Metaphor is an important tool in shaping the worldview through language. A person understands abstract concepts through concrete images. For example, the concept of time is associated with movement in many languages: in Uzbek *vaqt o'tmoqda*, in English *time flies*. Here time is imagined as a living being or a moving object.

Also, the concept of life is often expressed through the metaphor of a path: *hayot yo'li, to choose the right path*. This shows that a person perceives life as a goal-oriented action. Such metaphorical modeling reveals the cognitive foundations of the worldview through language.

4. Cultural code and semantic field.

Behind linguistic units, a cultural code is hidden, which reflects the values and stereotypes of a particular people. For example, in the Uzbek language *bread* is interpreted not only as food, but also as a symbol of holiness, blessing and life. Therefore, such combinations as *bread hit, to find bread* are widely used. In English, the word *bread* is used more in an economic sense (to earn one's bread). [7]

From the point of view of semantic field, each language divides certain concepts into central (core) and secondary (periphery) elements. For example, in the Uzbek language, the concept of *heart* has a very wide semantic field, which embodies emotions, mental states and internal experiences. In English, these meanings are divided into several separate units, such as *heart, mind, soul*.

5. Interaction between language and thinking.

The above examples show that language directly affects human thinking. The way a person names the world is how he perceives it. At the same time, thinking also enriches the language and causes the emergence of new units. This process is interconnected and continuous.

In conclusion, the formation of a worldview through language is a complex process that is carried out using lexical, phraseological and metaphorical means, determined by cultural and cognitive factors. Comparative study of different languages makes it possible to identify common and specific aspects of humanity's perception of the world.

List of used literatures:

1. Apresyan Yu. D.L. Лексическая семантика: синонимические средства языка. Moskva Nauka 2001. p.42
2. Fillmore C. J. *Frame Semantics*. New York Academic Press 2002. p.25
3. Humboldt W. von. *Language and Worldview*. Cambridge Cambridge University Press 1999. p.87
4. Jackendoff R. *Semantics and Cognition*. Cambridge MIT Press 1993. p.112
5. Lakoff G., Johnson M. *Metaphors We Live By*. Chicago University of Chicago Press 2000. p.147
6. Langacker R. W. *Cognitive Grammar: A Basic Introduction*. Oxford Oxford University Press 2008. p.23
7. Leech G. *Semantics: The Study of Meaning*. London Penguin Books 2011. p.17